

Noise Reduction in Actual Transient Measurement of Aircraft Lightning Testing utilizing Component A Generator with a Semiconductor Switch

Taro Ito*, Keisuke Kawamura†, Yoshifumi Ikeda*,
Seichi Kawasaki†, Yoichi Nakai* and Hideo Yamakoshi†

*Mitsubishi Aircraft Corporation, Japan (MITAC), taro.ito.mw@mhi.com,

†Mitsubishi Heavy Industries, Ltd., Japan (MHI), keisuke.kawamura.aq@mhi.com

Keywords: Lightning, Aircraft lightning test, Actual transient level, Electro-magnetic noise

1. ABSTRACT

A semiconductor switch is employed in Component A generator instead of conventional mechanical switch in aircraft lightning actual transient test. One order of magnitude noise reduction is observed in open circuit voltage responses. Causes of the noises are discussed. Electro-magnetic (EM) shielding at both ends of cables under test becomes unnecessary in most cases for Component A measurements with introduction of the semiconductor switch. Simple shielding for Component H measurements is developed considering frequency range and levels of noises associated with the Component H responses. The semiconductor switch of the generator shows durability through three thousand shots of operation.

2. INTRODUCTION

To support showing compliance with 14 CFR 25.1316 [1] of a transport aircraft, lightning aircraft test is usually conducted according to SAE ARP5412B [2], ARP5415B [3] and ARP5416A [4] in order to determine levels of lightning protections required for components and wirings of the aircraft.

High frequency noises observed in the test at the beginning of Component A and Component H responses are often headache in evaluating the actual transient levels since it is often difficult to distinguish Waveform 3 responses defined in SAE ARP5412B [2] from the noises due to similar oscillating frequencies. High amplitude noises sometimes even mask the actual transients. The main cause of the noises was believed to be radiation of EM field and possibly noise conduction to the measurement points or measurement system and/or arcing of mechanical switches used in conventional Current Component A generators.

Another issue of the mechanical switches of the generators is the fact that they sometimes require maintenance to keep both the proper shape of the waveform and the level of the noise low.

In this paper, application of component A generator with a semiconductor switch to lightning aircraft test is reported. The generator can deliver 1 kA of clean Component A waveform defined in ARP 5412B [2] into up to 20 μ H loads. Reduction of the noise of Component A responses is observed. And as a result, necessary EM-shielding for Component A measurement, which requires heavy and thick metal layer, is reduced. In addition, even though shielding for component H

is still necessary, it is significantly simplified because the shielding could be dedicated to Component H noises, which only requires light and thin aluminum foils in most of measurement points.

The durability of the semiconductor switch was also discussed.

3. TEST SETUP

The test setup described below is according to ARP5416A current pulse test.

3.1 Aircraft and Test Harness Setup

Test was conducted with Mitsubishi SpaceJet M90 aircraft. Sets of two attachment points which are entry and exit points for simulated lightning pulse injection are determined based on possible lightning scenarios to achieve the most severe lightning transient cases. Examples of the sets are Nose Radome Diverter to Tail Cone, Windshield Post to Winglet, Ram Air Turbine to Tail Cone, and Engine Inlet to Vertical Stabilizer Tip. Entry point is connected to the generator and exit point is connected to return conductors around the aircraft. Fig. 1 shows the test setup with the aircraft and the return conductors. The generator is not shown in the picture. EM field around the aircraft which is generated by the conductors, such as sixteen parallel return conductors along to the fuselage, is analyzed to make sure the field is uniformly formed to simulate actual lightning situation. The set of parallel sixteen conductors also make its round-trip circuit loop inductance low enough for the generators to deliver current pulses which meet Component A and Component H shapes.

Fig. 1. Aircraft test setup of Mitsubishi SpaceJet M90 with return conductors

Responses from many sets of harnesses and lightning scenarios are measured as required for purposes of type certification and engineering. In conclusion, results from a harness in a test bundle presented here are confirmed as typical results of the entire test except the cases with severe EM-field exposure as described later. The test bundle is

installed between Brake control equipment in Main Landing Gear Bay (Right Hand) and Flap Skew Sensor (Right Hand Inboard Flap) at Main Wing Trailing Edge as shown in Fig. 2. It consists of five single-shielded aircraft-grade harnesses with each end terminated to a connector with a two-inch pigtail. It is 5 m in length and tied to existing harnesses using tie straps. Measurements of open circuit voltage (V_{oc}), short circuit current (I_{sc}) and bundle current (I_{bc}) are done at both MLG bay side where relatively low EM noise environment is expected and trailing edge side where relatively high environment is expected.

(a) MLG Bay side of the test harness

(b) Trailing Edge side of the test harness in Main Wing root section (Right Hand)

Fig. 2. Installation of the test harness

3.2 Lightning Pulse Generators

The semiconductor-switch Component A generator, specially developed for actual transient aircraft tests, is used in the test. Fig. 3 shows views of the generator and its controller. Fig. 4 shows a typical current waveform of Component A applied to the aircraft from the generator. It can deliver 1kA into up to 20 μH loads which is sufficient for this aircraft test. Behlke thyristor switch model HTS 500-1200-SCR is used as the semiconductor switch.

Conventional mechanical-switch generators of Component A and Component H are also used for Component A noise level comparison and Component H noise reduction demonstration. Mechanical switches used for the Component A and Component H generators are Ross Engineering Corporation model E60-NC-80-1-100-BD. Component A is operated at 1 kA and Component H is operated at 100 A.

(a) Controller

(b) Generator

Fig. 3. Semiconductor-switch Component A generator

Fig. 4. Typical actual current waveform injected to the aircraft from the semiconductor-switch Component A generator

3.3 Measurement System

Measurement system, which was mainly provided by Element Material Technology, consists of Tektronix TDS3014C oscilloscopes, current transformers, home made voltage probes, personal computer, and communication devices. All instruments are calibrated. Injection current is measured by Pearson CT 110A current monitor. For V_{oc} and background (BGD) noise measurement, home made probes are used and directly connected to the oscilloscopes. Parallel resistor of 10 $k\Omega$ is used to reduce high frequency noise. SUHNER Double Shielded Coax S 04272 B (Flat Braid and Copper Sheet) is used to prevent EM field coupling through the cables as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. V_{oc} measurement probes

All transient measurement components such as probes, oscilloscopes and data transmitters are electrically isolated from ground, power lines and data receivers by using battery operation and optical communication in order to prevent noise conduction through the lines and human electrical shock and component damage due to high potential difference.

All oscilloscopes are synchronized by an optical trigger system similar to that used in our past test [5]. Fig. 6 shows typical aircraft transient test setup with the measurement devices.

Fig. 6. Typical aircraft transient test setup with measurement devices

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All voltage and current values used in this paper are normalized to standard Component A and H maximum levels of 200 kA and 10 kA, respectively, except for the actual values of semiconductor-switch generator output current in Fig. 4.

4.1 Noise Reduction of Component A Voc Response

Open circuit voltage (Voc) measurements are conducted using both the mechanical-switch generator and the semiconductor-switch generator. Fig. 7 shows typical principle of Voc measurement. No shielding for measurement points and the opposite ends of the test harness with such as aluminium foil was applied.

Each generator is connected to Engine Inlet which is an entry point of the test. Tail Cone, which is the exit point in the test, is connected to return conductors such that the current returns to the generator through all conductors evenly. Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 show the results measured in MLG bay and at trailing edge, respectively. In both Figs., (a) is whole Component A response with the mechanical-switch generator, and (b) is its front-end detail. (c) is whole response with the semiconductor-switch generator, and (d) is its front-end detail. Black solid lines in the Figs are Voc results, whereas red lines are BGD noise measured by an identical voltage probe placed near the measurement points shown in Fig. 7 and Fig. 10. having simulated measurement loop area and direction with the measurement.

The front-end noises peaked at about ± 900 V with the mechanical-switch generator both in MLG bay and at trailing edge. In contrast, clean response is obtained with the front-end noise peak reduced to almost negligible (about ± 30 V) with the semiconductor-switch generator. This proves that over one-order of magnitude noise reduction is achieved by introduction of the semiconductor-switch generator. Similar clean waveforms are seen in most of other measurement

points as well. Exceptions are Voc measurements of harnesses connected to external mounted components where (1) direct attachments are simulated or (2) grounding of the components is not sufficient, which may be caused by several cases. First case is that the skins where the components are bonded are made of composite materials. Second one is that appropriate bonding cannot be achieved due to material limitations. In those cases, it is required to shield the harness end to reduce the noise further. This will be discussed further in Section 4.4.

Fig. 7. Principle of Voc measurement

(a) Voc response (mechanical switch)

(b) Front-end part (mechanical switch)

(c) Voc response (semiconductor switch)

(d) Front-end part (semiconductor switch)

Fig. 8. Noises observed on Voc response (MLG Bay)

(a) Voc response (mechanical switch)

(b) Front-end part (mechanical switch)

(c) Voc response (semiconductor switch)

(d) Front-end part (semiconductor switch)

Fig. 9. Noises observed on Voc response (Trailing Edge)

Fig. 10. Typical setup of Voc probe and BGD probe

4.2 Discussion of Noise Paths

In this section, possible sources and paths of the noise are evaluated, which may contribute to further noise reduction for semiconductor-switch generator and noise reduction for conventional mechanical-switch generator. Since the noise is significantly reduced using semiconductor switch, the switch is considered as the source of the noise. However, there are several possibilities of paths of the noise transmitted from the switch and measured by the oscilloscope.

The first possibility of the noise path may be from the switch and conducted through the current injection circuit. Fig. 11 shows the first 1 μ s of the Component A current rise at which the switch noise is expected. Nevertheless, no major noise was seen. Fig. 12 shows frequency spectrum of the injection current. No spectrum was seen in high frequency band at least up to 10 MHz (CT 110A has its 3dB cut-off at 20 MHz) of both mechanical- and semiconductor-switch generators. The reason for having the input waveform "clean" of spurious transients may be because the high frequency noise of the mechanical switch is filtered out through the injection circuit.

(a) Mechanical switch

(b) Semiconductor switch

Fig. 11. Front-ends of Component A waveforms applied to the aircraft from both generators

(a) Mechanical switch

(b) Semiconductor switch

Fig. 12. Fourier spectrums of waveforms applied to the aircraft from Component A generators (Current amplitude extrapolated to 200 kA)

Second possibility to be discarded is the noise on the power and ground lines, as the oscilloscope is floating, being fed by a battery, as described Section 3.3.

As third one, EM field is propagated through air from the generators to a loop formed due to setting the Voc measurement probes at the measurement-end. The EM field is considered as the most dominant noise path. As it may be noticed that BGD noise shown as red dotted line in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 is very low and this does not seem to support the assumption. However, we have already confirmed after the test that the size and normal direction of BGD probe loop had not been set as identical to the measurement loop because we had not paid attention to the importance to set BGD loop identical to measurement loop. This assumption was supported by Component H noise measurement described later in Section 4.5.

Fourth possible path is the same EM field propagation to a loop formed at the opposite of measurement-end (short-end). Usually, this should not be a dominant cause because the loop of shorting the core wire is much smaller and less exposed compared to the measurement end. However, if the short-end is exposed to severe EM field, for example, in case it is located near the generator, this can show certain level of noise.

As fifth one, the EM field propagation interacts with the coax cable of the Voc probe as well as the oscilloscope can be possible noise path. However, these should not be dominant because the BGD noise levels are very low in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9.

Lastly, the same EM field may couple to the test harness shield and core wire directly, resulting in significant Voc noise. However, the possibilities are considered not to be noise path for the following reasons. For the shield coupling, no obvious noise is observed on Ibc of the harness. This means that the noise on Voc is not attributed to Ibc because Voc is Ibc times transfer impedance Z_t which is approximately DC resistance of the shields at Component A lightning frequency range. For the direct core wire coupling, the direct penetration ratio of EM field through the shield is not high so this should not be a dominant path.

4.3 Noise spectrum in Component A Voc

Fig. 13 shows spectrums of Voc responses to Component A. (a) is mechanical switch, (b) is semiconductor switch. (c) is mechanical switch but the vertical scale is set to be same with (b) semiconductor figure so that the spectrum levels are easily compared between (b) and (c). Black solid lines are spectrums of Voc responses, and red dotted lines are BGD measurements.

Spectrums of low frequency band, up to 7 or 8 MHz, gradually decreasing from the first peaks at 0 MHz in (b) and (c), are believed to include signal and small noise in both mechanical and semiconductor switch cases.

Several peaks in 18 - 37 MHz band, especially very large in (a) and (c) are believed to be the EM noises discussed in Section 4.2. Mechanism of generation of 18 - 37 MHz EM fields in both mechanical- and semiconductor-switch generator is not known.

(a) Mechanical switch

(b) Semiconductor switch

(c) Mechanical switch (Same vertical scale with (b))

Fig. 13. Fourier spectrum of first 2 μ s of open circuit voltage $+V_{oc}$ of Component A (MLG Bay)

4.4 Reduction of Heavy EM-Shielding and its Capability when Applied

As discussed in Section 4.1, noise is greatly reduced by the semiconductor switch and shielding for measurement points and the opposite ends of target harnesses with aluminium foil, metal sheet, metal braid etc. is not necessary any more in most of Component A measurements of Voc, Isc and Ibc.

Exceptions are (1) Voc measurements of harnesses connected to external mounted components where direct attachments are simulated, (2) those with which EM-field exposure is severe because the skins are made of composites, or insufficient bonding of components due to material restrictions. In such

cases, good EM-shielding of exposed ends are necessary to reduce the noise further. In Fig. 14, an example of EM-shielding is shown. The harness under test is for an antenna installed on CFRP structure covered by copper mesh. In the test, the harness is disconnected from the antenna and the core wire is shorted to the ground of the harness connector. This exposed end is covered by a thick over braid and connected to the antenna connector. Then, the over braid is further covered by a magnetic shielding sheet. As a result, Waveform 3 transient is reduced from 790 V to 290 V.

With the mechanical-switch generator, this type of heavy EM-shielding was necessary in many cases in our past aircraft test. With the semiconductor-switch generator, only several cases such as Weather Radar and Ram Air Turbine require this type of EM-shielding.

Fig. 14. EM-shielding in high EM-field location

4.5 Shielding Necessary in Component H Measurements

In the case Component H measurement is required according to ARP5415B, EM-shielding for Component H measurement may still be necessary. Fig. 15 shows typical Component H current waveform applied to the aircraft from mechanical-switch Component H generator in the test. Fig. 16 shows Voc Component H response in MLG Bay side of the same test harness with that in Section 4.1.

Fig. 17 shows Voc response of Component H as a function of number of aluminium (Al) foil layers as an EM-shielding covering the measurement-end of the test harness. Fig. 18 shows typical example of the Al foil layers covering the measurement-end of the test harness. The thickness of the Al foil is 25 μm per one foil. Black bars represent Voc probe signal levels. As the number of the layer increases, the level is decreased. Especially, the first one layer reduced the level significantly. Fig. 19 shows Fourier spectrum of Voc Component H response without the Al foil. The lowest frequency of major peak starts at 26 MHz and it peaks at 33 MHz. Since the skin depth of Al at 25 MHz is 16 μm , the significant noise reduction by one layer of the foil is reasonable. From Fig. 17, we concluded two layers of the foils should be sufficient to prevent the noise.

Red bars in Fig. 17 represent BGD levels. The BGD levels also showed similar decrease with the Voc signal. Black squares with solid lines represent Signal to BGD noise ratio. The ratio remains about 10 up to 4 layers foils. This is believed because the measured signal/noise are mainly generated at the measurement-end where both the signal and BGD probes are

located and are covered by the foils. The reason why the ratio is decreased to about 6 at 8 layers is probably because there are small noise sources somewhere other than at the shielded measurement-end.

As discussed in Section 4.1, by applying the semiconductor-switch Component A generator to aircraft lightning test, the number of measurement points where EM-shielding is necessary is significantly reduced. Even though that for Component H measurements are still necessary, only 2 layers of Al foils are sufficient. In the past, the heavy EM-shielding described in Section 4.4 was necessary for the most of all the Component A measurement points to reduce the noise level. With the semiconductor switch, the EM-shielding becomes much simpler where one or two layers of Al foils are only necessary for Component H measurement points. This reduces the lead time for the measurement preparation of the test significantly.

Fig. 15. Typical Component H current waveform applied to the aircraft from mechanical-switch Component H generator

Fig. 16. Voc Component H response (MLG side)

Fig. 17. Voc Component H response as a function of number of Aluminum foil layers covering the measurement-end of the test harness

Fig. 18. Typical example of the Aluminum foil layers covering the measurement-end of the test harness

Fig. 19. Fourier spectrum of first 2 μ s Voc Component H response

Fig. 20. Fourier spectrum of first 2 μ s waveform applied to the aircraft from the Component H generator

The frequency band of 26 – 42 MHz, seen in Voc Component H response in Fig. 19, is substantially higher than frequency spectrum of Component H defined in ARP 5412 or its differential waveform spectrum, which is 1 MHz or less, it should not be actual transient waveforms such as Waveform 4, 2 or 3.

Fig. 20 shows frequency spectrum of the injection current of Component H. No spectrum was seen in frequency band of 26 – 42 MHz. So, conduction noise on the injected current is not a cause of the Component H response.

4.6 Durability of Semiconductor Switch

The semiconductor switch of the generator is used over three months of the aircraft test. There is no trouble, no degradation of output waveform with about three thousand shots, which should be sufficiently durable for typical certification tests. No maintenance was necessary during this period. In comparison, the mechanical switch requires maintenance of electrode surface polish several times to keep noise level relatively low during this kind of duration. This proved the semiconductor-switch generator is well suited to aircraft lightning certification tests.

5. CONCLUSIONS

A semiconductor-switch Component A generator showed substantial noise reduction in Voc measurements. Causes of the noises were discussed. The need of EM-Shielding in the measurement points is significantly reduced to a few specific cases when a component A semiconductor-switch generator is used, and it is mainly relegated now to testing with component H injection. The semiconductor switch of the generator showed durability, sufficient for aircraft lightning certification tests. Future work would be to build a Component H generator with a semiconductor switch.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Authors would like to thank all the members who contributed to the development of the generator and the execution of the aircraft test. The generator was developed from advice of Dr. Yuichiro Kamino of MHI and by a collaboration between NTS Pittsfield Lightning Technologies, Shoshin Corporation, EMC Japan, MITAC and MHI. The aircraft test was conducted with a support from Element Materials Technology. Authors would like to thank Dr. Stephen Boag of Element for his dedicated online real time support from UK due to border closure for Covid situation, despite time difference.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] FAA, 14 CFR 25.1316, 'Code of Federal Regulations – Title 14 Aeronautics and Space – Part 25 Airworthiness Standards: Transport Category Airplanes – Electrical and electronic system lightning protection', 2011
- [2] SAE ARP5412B, 'Aircraft Lightning Environment and Related Test Waveforms', 2013
- [3] SAE ARP5415B, 'User's Manual for Certification of Aircraft Electrical/Electronic Systems for the Indirect Effects of Lightning', 2020
- [4] SAE ARP5416A: 'Aircraft Lightning Test Methods', 2013
- [5] Yuki Yano, Nobuyuki Kamihara, Yoichiro Tsumura, Kazuki Yamawaki, Toshihiko Nishimori, Tatsufumi Aoi, "Full Vehicle Test of Mitsubishi Regional Jet to Establish Lightning Transients Levels", ICOLSE 2017